

Supplementary Material for Owen Sampling Accelerates Contribution Estimation in Federated Learning

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1 Long-Tailed Class Distribution

Figure 1 shows how the MNIST label histogram changes after applying the three imbalance factors used in the main paper.

Figure 1: MNIST class counts before and after applying imbalance factors 0.1, 0.05, and 0.01.

2 Additional Accuracy Curves

Figures 2–6 report accuracy for all remaining Dirichlet–imbalance combinations ($\alpha \in \{0.01, 0.05, 0.1\}$; imbalance $\in \{0.01, 0.05\}$), using the same layout as the main-paper curves. Each plot averages three random seeds.

Across all settings, lower α or stronger imbalance slows convergence, but the ranking of methods is consistent with the main paper.

3 Baseline Algorithms

We give pseudocode for each baseline estimator used in Section 4 of the main paper. All baselines are executed under the same $N \times M$ evaluation budget and the shared ϵ -greedy scheduler described in Section 4.1.

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Figure 2: Imbalance 0.05, Dirichlet $\alpha = 0.01$.

Figure 3: Imbalance 0.01, Dirichlet $\alpha = 0.05$.

Figure 4: Imbalance 0.05, Dirichlet $\alpha = 0.05$.

Figure 5: Imbalance 0.01, Dirichlet $\alpha = 0.1$.

Figure 6: Imbalance 0.05, Dirichlet $\alpha = 0.1$.

1. MC-Shapley [1]. Randomly samples full permutations and averages marginal gains.

Algorithm 1 MC-Shapley approximation [1]

Require: Client set N , samples M

```
1:  $\phi_i \leftarrow 0$  for all  $i \in N$ 
2: for  $m = 1$  to  $M$  do
3:   Draw random permutation  $\pi$ , set  $S \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
4:   for  $i$  in  $\pi$  do
5:      $\phi_i += v(S \cup \{i\}) - v(S)$ 
6:      $S \leftarrow S \cup \{i\}$ 
7:   end for
8: end for
9: return  $\phi_i/M$ 
```

2. Data Banzhaf [2]. Estimates Banzhaf values by sampling random subsets instead of permutations.

Algorithm 2 Monte-Carlo Banzhaf approximation [2]

Require: Client set N , samples M

```
1:  $\beta_i \leftarrow 0$  for all  $i \in N$ 
2: for  $m = 1$  to  $M$  do
3:   Draw random subset  $S \subseteq N$ 
4:   for  $i \in N \setminus S$  do
5:      $\beta_i += v(S \cup \{i\}) - v(S)$ 
6:   end for
7: end for
8: return  $\beta_i/M$ 
```

3. GTG-Shapley [3]. Guided truncation skips marginal gains below a threshold ϵ .

Algorithm 3 GTG-Shapley approximation [3]

Require: Clients N , threshold ϵ , samples M

```
1:  $\phi_i \leftarrow 0$ , compute  $v(N)$ 
2: for  $m = 1$  to  $M$  do
3:   Draw permutation  $\pi$ , set  $S \leftarrow \emptyset$ ,  $v_{\text{prev}} \leftarrow 0$ 
4:   for  $i$  in  $\pi$  do
5:     if  $|v(N) - v_{\text{prev}}| \geq \epsilon$  then
6:        $v_{\text{curr}} \leftarrow v(S \cup \{i\})$ 
7:     else
8:        $v_{\text{curr}} \leftarrow v_{\text{prev}}$ 
9:     end if
10:     $\phi_i += v_{\text{curr}} - v_{\text{prev}}$ 
11:     $v_{\text{prev}} \leftarrow v_{\text{curr}}$ ,  $S \leftarrow S \cup \{i\}$ 
12:  end for
13: end for
14: return  $\phi_i/M$ 
```

4. WeightedSHAP (Beta-shaped) [4]. Applies Beta weights to favour early or late coalition positions.

Algorithm 4 WeightedSHAP approximation [4]

Require: Clients N , Beta parameters α, β , samples M

- 1: Pre-compute Beta weights w_j for $j = 1, \dots, |N|$, set $\phi_i \leftarrow 0$
 - 2: **for** $m = 1$ **to** M **do**
 - 3: Draw permutation π , set $S \leftarrow \emptyset$
 - 4: **for** $j = 1$ **to** $|N|$ **do**
 - 5: $i \leftarrow \pi[j]$, $\Delta \leftarrow v(S \cup \{i\}) - v(S)$
 - 6: $\phi_i += w_j \Delta$, $S \leftarrow S \cup \{i\}$
 - 7: **end for**
 - 8: **end for**
 - 9: **return** ϕ_i/M
-

5. ShapFed-WA [5]. Uses per-class Shapley values from last-layer gradients to weight aggregation.

Algorithm 5 ShapFed-WA aggregation [5]

Require: Class-specific gradients \hat{w}_i

- 1: Compute contribution scores γ_i via cosine similarity
 - 2: Normalise: $\tilde{\gamma}_i = \gamma_i / \sum_j \gamma_j$
 - 3: **return** $w_{\text{global}} = \sum_i \tilde{\gamma}_i \hat{w}_i$
-

References

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